

CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF SAMPRAPTI OF ORAL SUB MUCOUS FIBROSIS AND RANDOMIZED, OPEN LABELLED, CONTROLLED, CLINICAL STUDY OF EFFICACY OF KSHUDRADI KAVALA ON IT

*¹Dr. Pratibha Kondibarao Waghmare, ²Dr. Nisar Ali Khan

¹(Assistant Professor, Shalakyatantra Department, Government Ayurvedic College, Vazirabad Nanded Maharashtra 431601.)

²(HOD & Professor, Shalakyatantra Department, Government Ayurvedic College, Vazirabad Nanded Maharashtra 431601.).

Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Dec. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17963217>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Pratibha Kondibarao Waghmare

(Assistant Professor, Shalakyatantra Department, Government Ayurvedic College, Vazirabad Nanded Maharashtra 431601.)

How to cite this Article: *Dr. Pratibha Kondibarao Waghmare, Dr. Nisar Ali Khan. (2026). Conceptual Study of Samprapti of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis and Randomized, Open Labelled, Controlled, Clinical Study of Efficacy of Kshudradi Kavala on It. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(24), 1131–1155.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Oral sub mucous fibrosis is not mentioned in ayurvedic literature but it resembles mostly to common features of *Vataja Mukhpaka* and *Pittaja mukhpaka* to some extent. In *Astanga Hrudayam*, *kshudradi kavala* is advocated for treatment of all *Mukhrogas*. *Kshudradi kavala* have properties of *tridoshghna*, *mrudukar*, *vran ropan* which will treat the condition by decreasing inflammation, healing of lesions, softening the scar tissue and protect buccal mucosa, thus further irritation and damage from various toxins will be avoided. These Contents of *Kshudradi kavala* have properties to relieve complaints and break *samprapti* of oral sub mucous fibrosis. The drugs of this formulation are easily available and easy to use. Hence, this topic was selected for study. **Aim and Objectives:** To Study *Samprapti* of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis and the efficacy of *Kshudradi kavala* in the management of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis. **Methodology:** Patients reported to OPD of *Shalakyatantra* department were enrolled fulfilling inclusion

criteria for the study. Total 60 patients were enrolled and divided 30 in each group. Patients in Group A(n=30) were treated with *Kshudradi Kavala* and Patients in Group B (n= 30) were treated with *Tila taila saindhava gandushadharana* for 15 days. After completion of

treatment both the groups were assessed for objective (Ulceration number, Ulceration size, Oral mucosal lesions, Mouth opening, Fibrosis of mucosa) and subjective (Burning sensation, Dysphagia) criteria. **Results:** Significant improvement was observed in all parameters after completion of treatment in both groups. In comparison *Kshudradi kavala* dharana showed better improvement than *Tila taila saindhava gandusha* dharana in all parameters.

KEYWORDS: *mukhpaka, kshudradi kawal, oral submucous fibrosis, tila taila gandusha.*

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is the basic science which deals with the life of mankind. *Ayurveda* not only cares for the health of individual but it simultaneously provides prescriptions and prohibitions to treat diseases for the maintenance of healthy living.^[1]

Shalakyatantra is a specialized branch of *Ashtanga Ayurveda* deals with the causes, diagnosis and curative procedures of the diseases pertaining to the head, ear, nose, eye, orodental and throat. The name of the branch is so called because of use of '*Shalaka*' for treatment.^[2] The *Mukha* i.e. oral cavity, it is considered to be one of the most important parts of the *Urdhwajatru*.

In *Sutrasthana, Charaka & Sushruta* have given guidelines for daily care of oral cavity under heading *Dincharya* like as *Dant dhawana, Dhumapana, Kavala, Gandusha, Tambul sevana*,^[3] etc. Negligence of oral care may give rise to different oral diseases.

In *Nidan Sthana, Sushruta* has described the 65 *Mukha Rogas*. Diseases of oral cavity are found to attack seven different locations viz, lips, gums, teeth, tongue, palate, throat & entire oral cavity.^[4]

Tambul sevana, one method for keeping mouth healthy, is being practiced in Indian subcontinent since thousands of years. But *Tambul sevana* is diverted to tobacco and betel nut mixed pan, gutka, mava in this century due to considering them as stress relieving aid. Probably involved pathogenesis is stimulation of fibroblast production, increased collagen synthesis due to areca nut alkaloids mainly arecoline along with stabilization of collagen structures by catechin and tannin contents of areca nuts. It may lead to increase evidence of pathological changes in oral mucosa and causes oral sub mucous fibrosis.

Oral submucous fibrosis is an insidious chronic disease associated with juxtra epithelial inflammatory reaction followed by a fibro elastic change of lamina propia with epithelial atrophy leading to stiffness of oral mucosa causing burning sensation in mouth, inflammation and ulceration of oral mucosa, difficulty to open the mouth, loss of mobility of tongue, poor oral hygiene and its complications. If these persist for longer time it may lead to malignancy.^[5,6,7]

Oral sub mucous fibrosis is not mentioned in ayurvedic literature but it resembles mostly to common features of *Vataja Mukhpaka* and *Pittaja mukhpaka* to some extent. This disease is not mentioned in Ayurveda but according to *Sushruta Samhita*, none of diseases occur without *Dosha-Dushti*.^[8] Hence effort will be made to find out etiological factors, *Dosha-Dushti*, *Dhatu Dushti* i.e. *Samprapti*, sites of disease and presenting signs and symptoms of oral sub mucous fibrosis and relating them with ayurvedic principles of treatment and treated as per *Dosha lakshana*. According to *Charaka* name to each disease is not important but knowing its *Samprapti* and treating is the way of treatment.^[9]

Ulceration scattered all over oral cavity, dryness of lips, tongue becomes hypersensitive to cold, heavy and rough, difficulty to open mouth. Vesicles with piercing and tearing pain in mouth. These are the symptoms of *Vataja Mukhpaka*.^[10,11] Difficulty in mouth opening in *Vataja Mukhpaka* mentioned by *vagabhata* is one of the cardinal signs of oral submucous fibrosis. Burning sensation, pain, bitter taste of mouth and ulceration resembling like alkali burn occur in oral cavity. Red, yellow ulcers with severe burning sensation are symptoms of *Pittaja Mukhpaka*.^[12,13] On the basis of above-mentioned facts oral submucous fibrosis is *Vata Pittaj roga* causing *mansa* and *twacha dushti*, localising oral cavity.

Number of patients come across in OPD of Shalaky Tantra for Ayurvedic treatment as there is no definite and satisfactory treatment available for oral submucous fibrosis.

In *Astanga Hrudayam*, *kshudradi kavala* is advocated for treatment of all *Mukhrogas*.^[14] *Kshudradi kavala* have properties of *tridoshghna*, *mrudukar*, *vran ropan* which will treat the condition by decreasing inflammation, healing of lesions, softening the scar tissue and protect buccal mucosa, thus further irritation and damage from various toxins will be avoided. These Contents of *Kshudradi kavala* have properties to relieve complaints and break *samprapti* of oral sub mucous fibrosis.

AIM

“Conceptual Study of *Samprapti* Of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis and Randomized, Open Labelled, Controlled, Clinical Study of Efficacy of *Kshudradi Kavala* On It.”

OBJECTIVES**Primary Objective**

- To Study *Samprapti* of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis.
- To Study the efficacy of *Kshudradi kavala* in the management of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis.

Secondary Objective

- To Study etiological factors of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis.
- To Study the effect of *Kshudradi Kavala* on recurrent inflammation, ulceration and burning sensation of oral mucosa
- To Study the effect of *Kshudradi kavala* in improving trismus in Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis.

MATERIALS AND METHOD**CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF PATIENTS****1) Diagnostic criteria**

- Oral mucosal inflammation, discoloration, minute vesicle, ulceration.
- Oral pain and a burning sensation upon consumption of spicy foodstuffs.
- Progressive inability to open the mouth (trismus) due to oral sub mucosal fibrosis and scarring.
- Difficulty to protrude tongue.
- Dryness of the mouth.
- Impaired mouth movements. (e.g. eating, whistling, blowing, sucking.)

2) Inclusion Criteria

- Patients having Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis.
- Patients willing for clinical trials.
- Age – Above 12 years.
- Patients of both genders.

3) Exclusion Criteria

- Patient not willing for treatment.
- Other inflammatory conditions of oral cavity i.e. Candidiasis, Herpes stomatitis, oral lichen planus, diphtheria etc.
- Congenital deformities.
- Suspected or diagnosed malignancy.
- Temporomandibular joint disorders.
- Other systemic disease which may cause oral lesion. E.g. T.B.
- Uncontrolled diabetes mellitus.
- Severe anaemia i.e. Hb% < 7 gm/dl.
- Patients suffering from Erythroplakia.
- Patients on immunosuppressant therapy.
- Any other acute infections / febrile illness.
- Patients not willing to give up the habits of chewing gutka, tobacco.

4) Withdrawal Criteria

- Patient can be withdrawn from the trial if
 1. Occurrence of serious adverse event.
 2. The protocol has been violated or a patient has become un-co-operative.
 3. The patient is not willing to continue the trial or to follow the assessment schedule.

Grouping and Randomization of Patients

Selected patients were randomly divided into two groups by lottery method.

A) Group A – Trial group containing 30 patients.

B) Group B – Control group containing 30 patients.

Treatment given as follows

1. Group – A (Trial Group) – *Kshudradi kavala dharan*

- Dose – 50 ml
- Duration – twice in a day

2. Group - B (Control Group)- *Tila taila saindhav gandusha dharan*

- Dose – 50 ml
- Duration – twice in a day.

DRUG FORMULATION/DETAILS

Kantakari^[15], *Guduchi*^[16], *Jati*^[17], *Daruharidra*^[18,19], *Yawasa*^[20], *Triphala*^[21,22,23,24] these *dravya* take in same quantity as make 25 gm of *dravya* then add water 16 parts (400ml). Then mixture is boiled, stirred continuously till 1/8th of total mixture (50ml) remain.^[25] Then mix honey^[26] in the *kwatha*. This *kshudradi kwatha* is ready to use in mouth ulcers, oral sub mucous fibrosis. It acts as good *vranaropak*, *dahashaman*, *shoolaghna*, *shothaghna*.

Procedure of *kavala*^[27,28]***Purvakarma***

Patient will be kept in a room having less airflow in a comfortable posture and forehead, cheeks, neck region and shoulder will be gently massaged and fomented.

Pradhanakarma

The medicine will be made luke warm before use. The patient will be asked to take medicine in the oral cavity and keep mouth open and direct upward and asked to move liquid in whole oral cavity and throat. This will be done till the mouth becomes full of saliva, the nose and eyes start watering. Then the medicine can be spitted out and the procedure repeated if necessary. At a stretch three, five or seven gargles can be done to rid of the *doshas*.

Paschatkarma

After performing *kavala karma*, gentle massage and fomentation will be applied again.

Matra

Filling the mouth with half, one third and one fourth of its capacity is the *Pravara*, *Madhyama* and *Avara matra* respectively for *kavala dravya*. In this way 3, 5, 7-time *Aushada* should be held or till the *Doshanasha* is noticed.

Age limitation: *Kavala* can be in individuals above the age of 5years.^[29]

Dharana Kala^[30,31,32]

The procedure of *Kavala* should be practiced till the complete evacuation of *Dosha* is noticed; features like *Kaphapoorna Asyata*, *Netra Grana Srava* are seen. Though this procedure can be done anytime of the day, morning hours are ideal. After performing *Dantadhavana*, *Kavala* is indicated in *Dinacharya*.

Follow up: 0, 7th, 15th, 30th Day of treatment.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA**SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA****1) Burning sensation (*Daha*)****Table no. 1**

Sr.no.	Grades	Features
1	0	No complaints of burning
2	1	Burning sensation felt on taking spicy food
3	2	Burning sensation felt on taking normal food
4	3	Burning sensation felt throughout the day without any aggravating factors

2) Dysphagia (*Gilankashtata*)**Table no.2**

Sr.no.	Grades	Features
1	0	Patient can swallow any type of food easily
2	1	Difficulty in swallowing solids
3	2	Difficulty in swallowing with nasal reflux

OBJECTIVE CRITERIA**1) Ulceration Number (*Vrana/Sphota*)****Table no. 3**

Sr.No.	Grades	Features
1	0	No ulceration
2	1	< 2 ulcers
3	2	2-4 ulcers
4	3	>4 ulcers

2) Ulceration size (*Vrana/Sphota*)**Table no.4**

Sr.no.	Grades	Features
1	0	No Ulceration
2	1	1-2 mm
3	2	4-6 mm
4	3	>6 mm

3) Oral mucosal lesions**Table no. 5**

Sr. no.	Grades	Features
1	0	Normal mucosa
2	1	Patchy redness
3	2	Vesicle formation
4	3	Superficial ulceration

4) Mouth opening

Opening of mouth will be measured by measuring distance between central incisors in open mouth by Vernier's caliper. It will be recorded in each follow up.

5) Fibrosis of mucosa**Table no.6**

Sr.no.	Grades	Features
1	0	No fibrosis of mucosa
2	1	Fibrosis of only buccal mucosa
3	2	Fibrosis of buccal and labial mucosa
4	3	Fibrosis of buccal, labial mucosa and palate

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS WITHIN GROUP A AND GROUP B**WILCOXON SIGNED RANKS TEST FOR QUALITATIVE DATA****Table No. 7- Wilcoxon signed Ranks Test to symptoms in the Group A.**

Symptoms	BT/AT	N	Mean	SD	W	P	Significant or Insignificant
Burning Sensation	BT	30	1.9	0.803	-465	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.2	0.406			
Dysphagia	BT	30	0.2	0.406	- 3	0.5000 (p>0.05)	Insignificant
	AT	30	0.133	0.345			
Ulceration Number	BT	30	1.366	0.927	-276	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.133	0.345			
Ulceration Size	BT	30	1.166	0.791	-276	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.133	0.345			
Oral mucosal lesions	BT	30	2.633	0.718	-465	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly significant
	AT	30	0.133	0.345			
Fibrosis of mucosa	BT	30	1.9	0.758	-15	0.0625 (p>0.05)	Insignificant
	AT	30	1.733	0.944			

PAIRED t TEST FOR QUANTITATIVE DATA**Table No. 8 - Paired t test to Symptom in the Group A.**

Symptom	BT/AT	N	Mean	SD	T	P	Significant or Insignificant
Mouth opening	BT	30	2.363	0.532	2.757	0.0100 (p<0.05)	Significant
	AT	30	2.423	0.578			

WILCOXON SIGNED RANKS TEST FOR QUALITATIVE DATA**Table No. 9 – Wilcoxon signed Ranks Test to symptoms in the Group B.**

Symptoms	BT/AT	N	Mean	SD	W	P	Significant or Insignificant
Burning Sensation	BT	30	1.96	0.718	-465	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.4	0.498			

Dysphagia	BT	30	0.233	0.430	-1	>0.9999 (p>0.05)	Insignificant
	AT	30	0.2	0.406			
Ulceration Number	BT	30	1.4	0.621	-406	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.333	0.479			
Ulceration Size	BT	30	1.26	0.583	-378	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.333	0.479			
Oral mucosal lesions	BT	30	2.733	0.827	-406	<0.0001 (p<0.05)	Highly Significant
	AT	30	0.466	0.571			
Fibrosis of mucosa	BT	30	2.033	0.556	-15	0.0625 (p>0.05)	Insignificant
	AT	30	1.866	0.730			

PAIRED t TEST FOR QUANTITATIVE DATA

Table No. 10 - Paired t test to Symptom in the Group B.

Symptom	BT/AT	N	Mean	SD	T	P	Significant or Insignificant
Mouth opening	BT	30	2.27	0.459	2.664	0.0125 (p<0.05)	Significant
	AT	30	2.32	0.519			

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS IN BETWEEN THE GROUP A AND GROUP B BY MANN WHITNEY'S U TEST FOR QUALITATIVE DATA

A) Burning Sensation

Table no. 11 - Mann Whitney's Test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	U	P
Group A	30	1.7	0.651	405	0.5076 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	1.56	0.568		

B) Dysphagia

Table no. 12 - Mann Whitney's Test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	U	P
Group A	30	0.066	0.2537	435	>0.999 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	0.033	0.1825		

C) Ulceration Number

Table no. 13 - Mann Whitney's Test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	U	P
Group A	30	1.233	0.897	399	0.4012 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	1.066	0.449		

D) Ulceration Size

Table no. 14 - Mann Whitney's Test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	U	P
Group A	30	1.033	0.718	413.5	0.6503 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	0.933	0.365		

E) Oral mucosal lesions

Table no. 15- Mann Whitney's Test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	U	P
Group A	30	2.5	0.731	381	0.2453 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	2.26	0.868		

F) Fibrosis of mucosa

Table no. 16 - Mann Whitney's Test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	U	P
Group A	30	0.1666	0.3790	450	>0.9999 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	0.1666	0.3790		

UNPAIRED t TEST FOR QUANTITATIVE DATA

A) Mouth opening

Table No. 17 - Unpaired t test in between the Group A and Group B.

Group	N	Mean	SD	T	P
Group A	30	-0.06	0.1191	0.3413	0.7341 (p>0.05)
Group B	30	-0.05	0.1074		

Effect of therapy

Table No. 18- Relieved score and % Relief in symptoms of Group A.

Sr.No.	Symptoms (Group A)	BT	AT	Relieved	% Relief
1	Burning sensation	57	6	51	89.47%
2	Dysphagia	6	4	2	33.33%
3	Ulceration number	41	4	37	90.24%
4	Ulceration size	35	4	31	88.57%
5	Oral mucosal lesions	79	4	75	94.93%
6	Mouth opening	70.9	72.7	-1.8	-2.538%
7	Fibrosis of Mucosa	57	52	5	8.771%
Average Relief (A)					58.26%

Table No. 19 - Relieved score and % Relief in Symptoms of Group B.

Sr.No.	Symptoms (Group B)	BT	AT	Relieved	% Relief
1	Burning sensation	59	12	47	79.66%
2	Dysphagia	7	6	1	14.28%
3	Ulceration number	42	10	32	76.19%
4	Ulceration size	38	10	28	73.68%
5	Oral mucosal lesions	82	14	68	82.92%
6	Mouth opening	68.1	69.8	-1.7	-2.49%
7	Fibrosis of Mucosa	61	56	5	8.19%
Average Relief (A)					48.20%

Average % Relief in symptoms

Table No. 20- Shows Average % Relief in Symptoms.

Sr No.	Group	Average % Relief in symptom score
1	Group A	58.26%
2	Group B	48.20%

Table no. 21: Overall Effect of Therapy according % Relief.

Sr. No.	Criteria	Improvement Grade	No. of patients	
			Gr. A	Gr. B
1	>75%	Excellent/Marked	17	08
2	51% to 75%	Moderate	06	13
3	25% to 50%	Mild	07	09
4	<25%	Ineffective/Poor	00	00

$$X^2 = 6.0689$$

$$p = 0.0481 (p < 0.05)$$

In group A, 17 patients shown marked improvement, 6 patients show moderate improvement, 7 patients show mild improvement. Hence, we can conclude that *Kshudradi kavaladharana* is effective in oral submucous fibrosis.

In group B, 8 patients shown marked improvement, 13 patients show moderate improvement, 9 patients show mild improvement. Hence, we can conclude that *Tila taila saindhav gandushadharana* is effective in oral submucous fibrosis.

The Chi-square Statistic is $X^2 = 6.0689$ and $p = 0.0481$ ($p < 0.05$). hence, the result is significant that is the trial group is more effective than control group.

Table no. 22- Improvement in mouth opening.

Group	Improved	Not improved	Total
Trial	7	23	30
Control	6	24	30
Total	13	47	60

$$\chi^2 = 0.09819$$

$$p = 0.754 (p > 0.05)$$

In group A, out of 60 patients 7 patients show improvement in mouth opening, while 23 patients show not improvement.

In group B, out of 60 patients 6 patients show improvement in mouth opening, while 24 patients show not improvement.

The Chi-square Statistic is $\chi^2 = 0.09819$ and $p = 0.754$ ($p > 0.05$). hence, the result is insignificant that is the trial group and control group both are equally effective in improving mouth opening.

Images of mouth opening before and after trial drug treatment

Before treatment

After treatment

DISCUSSION

1. Discussion on Review of literature

Oral submucous fibrosis is not mentioned in Ayurveda but according to *Sushruta Samhita*, none of diseases occur without *dosha-dushti*. Hence effort made to find out etiological factors, *dosha-dushti*, *dhatu dushti* i.e. *Samprapti*, sites of disease and presenting signs and symptoms of oral sub mucous fibrosis and relating them with ayurvedic principles of treatment and treated as per *dosha lakshana*.

According to *charaka* name to each disease is not important but knowing its *samprapti* and treating is the way of treatment.

Clinical features of oral submucous fibrosis i.e. recurrent stomatitis, intolerance of spices, scattered inflamed patches and burning sensation indicate *pitta dushti*. Dryness of mouth, hardening of mucosa and submucosal tissue, fibrous bands leading to difficult to mouth opening indicate *sankoch* and stricture of tissue indicate *vayu dushti*.

Oral submucous fibrosis is a chronic insidious process characterized by juxtraepithelial deposition of fibrous tissue in the oral cavity and pharynx. It is a chronic debilitating disease and a well-recognized potentially premalignant condition of the oral cavity. various medical and surgical treatment modalities have been used in modern science, but results are not satisfactory owing to recurrence, adverse effects and sometimes worsening the condition.

On analysing the disease condition with ayurvedic approach, it seems to be nearer to *vata-pitta* dominant chronic *sarvasara mukhroga* and needs to be treated at local level. The predisposing factors of OSMF are continuous use of tobacco, betel nut, gutka with dietary deficiencies.

Different treatment modalities like *Swedana*, *Virechana*, *Vamana*, *Gandusha*, *Pratisaran*, *Kavala*, *Raktmokshan*, *Nasya*, *Dhuma* have been described for the management of *Mukhrogas*.

Therefore, all the texts of Ayurveda emphasize more on local therapy for Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis like *Mukhrogas*.

Proper absorption of the active principles of drugs take place in the oral cavity due to direct local contact, local maximum concentration availability, and pressure massage effect created

by the action of *Kavala*. So, *Kavala* can play an important role in management of oral submucous fibrosis. In *Astanga hrudiyam*, *Kshudradi kavala* is advocated for treatment of all *mukhrogas*. Contents of *Kshudradi kavala* have properties to relieve complaints of oral submucous fibrosis.

2. Discussion on *Samprapti Vighatana*

For *Samprapti Vighatana*, *Nidana Parivarjana* is important so prevent *Samanyanidana* of *Mukharoga*, *Kaphaprapak*, *vata pitta prakopak*– *Ahitakar Ahara-Vihara* and disease treatment is given according to *Sadhyata*. Emphasis was also given on life style modification by motivating all patients to discontinue tobacco, betel nut and alcohol. Taking in consideration of *Samprapti* of the Oral submucous fibrosis, selected drug has following properties beneficial for *Samprapti Bhanga*.

***Kshudradi kavala* have following properties**

1. *Tridoshghna*
2. *Mrudukar*
3. *Vranropan*
4. *Vedanasthapan*
5. *Shothhar*
6. *Raktashodhak*
7. *Raktavardhak*
8. *Dahprashaman*
9. *Vranashodhan*
10. *Rasayan*
11. *Vilekhan*
12. *Srotovishodhan*

These properties helped to treat the condition by decreasing inflammation, healing of lesions, softening the scar tissue and protecting buccal mucosa, thus further irritation and damage from various toxins is avoided.

***Shodhaniya* and *Vranaropaniya* properties**

By *Katu*, *Tikta Rasa* and *Katu Vipaka* this drug acts as *Shodhaniya*. By *Kashaya Rasa* it acts as *Vranaropaka* also. It aggravates *Vata*, scrapes *Kapha* and normalizes *Pitta* and *Rakta*. And hence promotes and improve oral mucosal status, growth of healthy tissue.

Raktadhatu Prasadaka and Rakta Shodhaka properties

As in Oral submucous fibrosis *Rakta* is main *Dushya*. Our drug acts on *Rakta Dhatu*, content of this drug such as *Amalaki*, *yawasa* and *madhu* by its *Madhur Vipaka* along with *Sheet Veerya* does the *Prasadana Karya* by reducing the *Ushna – Tikshnta of Pitta* which is main cause of *Rakta Dushti*. According to *Sushrutacharya Dhatukshaya* and *Vrudhi* depend on the nature of *Rakta Dhatu*. And *Kshudradi kavala* is acting on *Rakta Dhatu* and *Raktavaha Srotas*.

Vednasthapana and Shothghna

Kantakari, *Guduchi*, *jati*, *daruharidra*, *haritaki*, *bibhitaki*, *yawasa* have properties of *Vednasthapana* and *Shothaghna*. *veerya* of *kantakari*, *daruharidra*, *haritaki*, *bibhitaki* is *Ushna* hence, these act as *Shothagna* property.

Rasayana and Dahaprashaman

Guduchi, *haritaki*, *amalaki* have properties of *Rasayana karma*. This improves *preenan* and overall immunity which in turns increases the strength of oral mucosa and submucosa. *Guduchi* and *amalaki* by their *Madhur vipak* perform *dahaprashman karma*.

Vilekhan and srotovishodhan

Madhu acts as *vilekhan*, *shothaghna* and *srotovishodhan karma* by its *laghu*, *ruksha* and *sukshma guna* which reverses fibrosis in some extent.

Probable mode of action of trial drug**❖ Effect of trial drug on Burning sensation**

Guduchi and *amalaki* by their *Madhur vipak* play *dahaprashman karma*. *Kantakari*, *Guduchi*, *jati*, *daruharidra*, *haritaki*, *bibhitaki*, and *yawasa* have properties of *Vednasthapana* and *Shothaghna*. hence reduce burning sensation.

❖ Effect of trial drug on Dysphagia

Madhu by *Srotovishodhan karma* and *jati* by *mukhroganashak karma*, reducing chronic inflammation and softening fibrotic tissues, reduces dysphagia.

❖ Effect of trial drug on Ulceration number, Ulceration size and Oral mucosal lesions

Jati, *daruharidra*, *haritaki*, *madhu* by their *vranashodhan* and *vranaropan* action reduce ulcerations and oral mucosal lesions.

❖ Effect of trial drug on Mouth opening

Overall effect of the drug relief in reducing inflammation, *shothgna*, healing ulcers, relaxing scar tissues by fibrolytic activity and releasing reflex spasm of the muscles and relaxing retromolar area mouth opening is increased.

❖ Effect of trial drug on fibrosis of mucosa

Madhu acts as *vilekhan* and *srotovishodhan karma* by its *laghu*, *ruksha* and *sukshma guna* which reverses fibrosis in some extent.

❖ Effect of trial drug on Dosha

Most of *Dravyas* of *Kshudradi kavala* are *Tridosahara*; they help in *Samprapti Vighatana* of Oral submucous fibrosis.

❖ Effect of trial drug on Dhatu

In *Kshudradi kavala dravyas* like *Amalaki* and *yawasa* has *Raktashamaka properties* and *haritaki* act as *rasayana dravya* which increases *rasa*, *rakta* and other *dhatu*, there by increases the strength of the body and helps in preventing diseases. These *Dravyas* help in *Samprapti Vighatana* of Oral submucous fibrosis.

Kshudradi kavala has fibrolytic, anti-inflammatory, wound cleaning, wound healing and *vata-pitta* dominant *Tridosha* pacifying effect as well as antioxidant properties. Hence, the drug is helpful in *Samprapti Vighatana* of Oral submucous fibrosis.

Thus, from all of above discussion, we can say that result obtained from trial drug was more significant than control drug in Oral submucous fibrosis.

3. Discussion on mode of action of *Kshudradi kavaladharana*

Kshudradi kavala have properties of *tridoshghna*, *mrudukar*, *vran ropan* which will treat the condition of oral submucous fibrosis by decreasing inflammation, healing of lesions, softening the scar tissue and protect buccal mucosa, thus further irritation and damage from various toxins will be avoided.

During the procedure of *kavala* due to withholding of the *dravya* and its movement within the oral cavity, pressure is created. So, this increased pressure stimulates pressoreceptor (stretch reflex) that are present in the mouth. Once the pressoreceptor is stimulated, they send signals to salivary nuclei in the brain stem and so the secretion of the saliva is increased. An enzyme

called lysozyme present in the saliva is bacteriostatic in action. It prevents the growth of pathogenic microorganism in the oral cavity. Antibody IgA present in saliva also provide protection against microorganisms.

Due to continuous movement of *dravya* within the oral cavity, the pressure created will wash of the debris from the oral cavity. When the contents of the oral cavity are spit, the microorganisms present in the oral cavity are washed off.

The act of *kavala* gives proper exercise to the muscles of cheeks, tongue, lips and soft palate there by increasing the motor functions of these muscles and strengthening the muscles of oral cavity. Which leads to relief from trismus and improves mouth opening in oral submucous fibrosis.

Hence, *kavaldharana* as a local therapy prevent and reverse fibrosis by improving blood circulation and better absorption of these drugs.

4. Discussion on Observation and Statistical Analysis

A. DEMOGRAPHIC DISCUSSION

Age – Patients age of above 12 years were selected, out of 60 patients maximum i.e. 33.33% of patients were from age group 41 to 50 yrs in both groups. So, from these we can conclude that frequency of addiction and early start of addiction are mostly seen in these age group.

Gender – Both male and female patients were randomly selected, out of 60 patients, 48(80%) were male patients and 12 (20%) were female patients. It was observed that male patients were more affected than female patients to oral submucous fibrosis. Male predominance in our study can be due to easy accessibility for males to use areca nut and its products more frequently than females.

Religion- Out of the total 60 patients affected by Oral submucous fibrosis Hindu and Muslims were 48 and 12 no. respectively. Hence, we can conclude that number of hindu patients were more affected than muslim patients by oral submucous fibrosis.

Occupation- Out of 60 patients 12 patients (20%) were Students, 9(15%) patients were housewife, 13(21.66%) patients were farmer, 9(15%) Patients were worker, 7(11.66%) patients were drivers and 10(16.66%) patients were businessman. hence, no specific relation found.

Education wise distribution- Out of the total 60 patients affected by Oral submucous fibrosis Literate educational status and Illiterate educational status were 35(58.33%) and 25(41.66%) in no. respectively in both groups. Hence, no specific relation found.

Residence- Out of 60 patients, 23(38.33%) patients were from Rural and 37 (61.66%) patients were from Urban population. Hence, urban population were more affected than rural may be due to excessive use of addictions as a stress relieving aids.

Socioeconomic status- Out of the total 60 patients, affected by Oral submucous fibrosis middle economic status and poor economic status were 27 and 33 in no. respectively. Hence, poor economic status was more affected may be due to lack of nutritional deficiencies.

Diet – Out of 60 patients, in trial group there were 10(33.33%) and 20(66.66%) no. of vegetarian and mixed diet status patients respectively. It seems to be true that among various *nidana* mentioned for *mukha roga* like excessive consumption of *anoop mamsa*, *matsya*, *varaha mamsa* is highlighted. Here in this study high incidence is found in mixed group with intake of *matsya* and *mamsa aahara*. Hence, mixed diet patients were affected may be due excessive consumptions of spicy foods.

Addiction- Out of 60 patients, Maximum 44(73.33%) patients had multiple addictions, 8(13.33%) patients had gutka addiction. While 6(10%) patients had tobacco addiction and 2(3.33%) patients had betel nut addiction. Hence, we conclude that all patients were addicted to gutka, tobacco, betel nut chewing.

Age at starting of addiction- In this study maximum numbers of patients i.e. 20(33.33%) patients start their habits between 21 to 25 yrs, 14(23.33%) patients start their habits between 10 to 15 yrs of age. While 13(21.66%) patients start their habits between 16 to 20 yrs and 26 to 30 yrs of age. Hence, we conclude that more rapid progression of oral submucous fibrosis when the habit is taken at an earlier age.

Prakruti- In this study, 45% patients had *vata pitta prakruti*, 28.33% patients had *pitta vata prakruti* and 10% patients had *pitta kapha prakruti*. 6.66% patients had *vata kapha* and *kapha vata prakruti* while 3.33% patients had *kapha pitta prakruti*. The *Vata-pitta prakruti* people were mostly affected owing to similarities of disease initiating doshas.

B. CLINICAL DISCUSSION

Subjective Parameters (By Wilcoxon Singed Ranks Test)

A) Burning sensation

Since observations are on ordinal scale, we have used Wilcoxon singed rank test to test the significance in each group.

- For trial group from above table we can observe that value of p is less than 0.05, hence we conclude that there is significant change observed after treatment.

For control group from above table we can observe that value of p is less than 0.05, hence we conclude that there is significant change observed after treatment.

When Mann whitneys test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below-

- p value is more than 0.05, statistically it is concluded that trial drug and control drug both are equally effective.

B) Dysphagia

Since observations are on ordinal scale, we have used Wilcoxon singed rank test to test the significance in each group.

- For trial group as value of p is greater than 0.05, Insignificant difference was observed after treatment.
- For control group as value of p is greater than 0.05, Insignificant difference was observed after treatment.

When Mann whitneys test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below-

- p value is more than 0.05, statistically it is concluded that trial drug and control drug both are equally effective. But this parameter was present in very few patients of Group A and Group B. Hence definite conclusion cannot be made.

Objective Parameters

C) Ulceration Numbers

Since observations are on ordinal scale, we have used Wilcoxon singed rank test to test the significance in each group.

- For trial group as value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed after treatment.

- For control group as value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed after treatment.

When Mann whitneys test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below-

- p value is more than 0.05, statistically it is concluded that trial drug and control drug both are equally effective.

D) Ulceration Size

Since observations are on ordinal scale, we have used Wilcoxon signed rank test to test the significance in each group.

- For trial group as value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed after treatment.
- For control group as value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed after treatment.

When Mann whitneys test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below-

- p value is more than 0.05, statistically it is concluded that trial drug and control drug both are equally effective.

E) Oral mucosal lesions

Since observations are on ordinal scale, we have used Wilcoxon signed rank test to test the significance in each group.

- For trial group as value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed after treatment.
- For control group as value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed after treatment.

When Mann whitneys test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below-
p value is more than 0.05, statistically it is concluded that trial drug and control drug both are equally effective.

F) Fibrosis of mucosa

Since observations are on ordinal scale, we have used Wilcoxon signed rank test to test the significance in each group.

- For trial group as value of p is greater than 0.05, Insignificant difference was observed after treatment.
- For control group as value of p is greater than 0.05, Insignificant difference was observed after treatment.

When Mann whitneys test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below- p value is more than 0.05, statistically it is concluded that trial drug and control drug both are equally effective.

G) Mouth opening

Since observations are on nominal scale, we have used Paired t test to test the significance in each group.

Group A

As value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed between mean of BT and AT score in mouth opening parameter. Hence it is concluded that *Kshudradi kavaladharana* is effective to improve mouth opening in oral submucous fibrosis.

Group B

As value of p is less than 0.05, significant difference was observed between mean of BT and AT score in mouth opening parameter. Hence it is concluded that *Tila taila saindhav gandushadharana* is effective to improve mouth opening in oral submucous fibrosis.

When Unpaired t test was applied to compare both groups result observes given below- The calculated p value is 0.7341 which is insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. so, the trial drug and control drug equally effective in improving mouth opening.

OVERALL ASSESMENT CRITERIA

Depend on improvement in subjective parameter and objective parameter final assessment was done.

- In Group of *Kshudradi kavaladharana* (Group A) out of 60 patients' excellent relief in subjective and objective criteria was noted in 17 patients, moderate relief in 6 patients and mild improvement in 7 patients and ineffective in 0 patient.
- In Group of *Tila taila saindhav gandushadharana* (Group B) Excellent relief in subjective and objective criteria was noted in 8 patients, moderate relief in 13 patients, mild improvement in 9 patients and ineffective in 0 patient.

Finally, in trial group the number of patients with marked improvement was more than number of moderate improved patients and not improved patients as compared to control group.

CONCLUSION

1. oral submucous fibrosis can be correlated with *vataj* and *pittaj sarvasar mukhroga* due to similarity of symptoms.
2. oral submucous fibrosis is found predominantly in middle age group individuals in our study.
3. Addiction and age at early start of addiction plays an important role.
4. Improvement observed in clinical assessment after 7 days of treatment in trial group and in control group improvement occurs after 15 days.
5. Clinically and statistically improvement was observed in burning sensation, ulceration numbers, ulceration size, oral mucosal lesions and mouth opening in both groups equally.
6. *Kshudradi kavaladharana* is proved to be more effective than *Tila taila saindhav gandushadharana* in oral submucous fibrosis such as burning sensation, ulceration numbers, ulceration size, oral mucosal lesions and mouth opening without any side effects.
7. There is no improvement in fibrosis of mucosa and dysphagia.
8. These effects are results of *vranaropan*, *mrudukar*, *lekhan*, *rasayana*, *vata pitaa shamak* properties of *Kshudradi kavaladharana*.
9. No adverse reaction of *kavaladharana* and *gandushadharana* is observed.
10. Mouth opening is improved significantly but fibrous bands are not disappeared completely. So, result is not encouraging in respect of fibrous bands. Further research can be carried out to get relieved from fibrosis completely with different approach

REFERENCES

1. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi – Charaka Samhita of Agnivesa Edited with ‘Caraka-Chandrika’ Hindi Comentary, Vol. I , Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprint year 2013; Cha.Su. 30/26, Page no.565.
2. Kaviraj Ambikadatta Shastri – Sushrut Samhita of Maharshi Sushruta Edited with Ayurveda-Tattva-Sandipika Part I, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Reprint Year 2014; Su.Su. 1/10., Page no.5.
3. Dr. Bhrumhanand Tripathi- Astang Hrudayam (Sutrasthana), Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, edition reprint 2017; Page No.29. Dinacharya Adhyaya 2/6.

4. Vd. Ambikadatta Shastri- Sushrut Samhita Part-I (Purvardha), Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, edition reprint 2015. Page No. 381 verse Sushrut Nidansthan 16/3.
5. Shafers Textbook of Oral pathology, Adaptation Editor B Sivapathasundaram.
6. K.B. Bhargava, S.K. Bhargava- ENT Diseases 9th Edition, Reprint -June 2012.
7. PL Dhingara/Shruti Dhingara-ENT & HEAD AND NECK SURGERY 7TH EDITION, REPRINT 2018.
8. Kaviraja Dr. Ambikadatta Shastri- Sushrut Samhita Part-1 (Purvardha), Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, edition reprint-2012; 171, Aaturopkramaniya Adhyaya 35/23.
9. Acharya Vidyadhar Shukla, Prof. Ravidatta Tripathi- Charaka Samhita-volume 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, edition reprint, 2011; 281. Trishothiya Adhyaya 18/44-45.
10. Dr. Brumhananda Tripathi- Astanga Hrudayam (uttarsthana) Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, edition reprint, 2017, Mukhrogavigyaniya Adhyaya 21/58-59. Page No. 1032.
11. Kaviraja Dr. Ambikadutta Shastri- Sushruta Samhita, Part-1, Nidansthana, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2012, Mukhroganidana Adhyaya, Page No. 392, Shlok No. 67.
12. Dr. Bhrumhanand Tripathi- Astang Hrudayam (uttarsthana), Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthana, edition reprint, 2017 Page No. 1033. Mukhrogavigyaniyam Adhyaya 21/61.
13. Kaviraja Dr. Ambikadutta Shastri - Sushruta Samhita, Part-1, Nidansthana, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2012, Mukhroganidana Adhyaya, Page No.392, Shlok No.
14. Dr. Bhrumhanand Tripathi- Astang Hrudayam (Uttarsthana), Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, edition reprint, 2017; Page No.1047 Mukharogapratishedha Adhyaya 22/97.
15. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2007; Page No.290, Guduchyadi Varga, Shlok. No. 40-41.
16. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2007; Page No. 269, Guduchyadi Varga, Shlok No. 8,9,10.
17. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2007; Page No. 491, Pushpa Varga, Shlok No. 28.
18. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha

- Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2007; Page No.116, Haritkyadi Varga, Shlok No.202.
19. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint, 2007; Page No.5, Haritkyadi Varga, Shlok No.23.
 20. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint 2007; Page No.411, Guduchyadi Varga, Shlok No.212-213.
 21. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint 2007, Page No.12, Haritkyadi Varga, Shlok No.43.
 22. Ganga Sahay, Krishnachandra Chunekar- Bhavprakash Nighantu, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, 2006, Page No. 5, Haritkyadi Varga.
 23. Shree. Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint 2007, Page No.9, Haritkyadi Varga, Shlok No.36.
 24. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi – Charaka Samhita of Agnivesa Edited with ‘Caraka-Chandrika’ Hindi Comentary, Vol. I, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprint year 2013, Cha.Su. 27/148,149. Page no.519.
 25. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi - Sharangdhar Samhita, Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi, reprint-2016, Madhyamkhand, Adhaya No.2, Page No.91, Shlok No. 1,2.
 26. Shree Brahmasankara Misra, Shree Rupalalaji Vaisya Bhavprakash Part 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint 2007, Page No.788, Madhu Varga, Shlok No.1-5.
 27. Kaviraja Dr. Ambikadutta Shastri - Sushruta Samhita, Chikitsasthana Part-1, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint-2017, Dhumnasyakavalgruhachikitsa Adhyaya Page No.229, Shlok No.62.
 28. Dr. Ravidutta Tripathi - Astanga samgraha, sutrasthana, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishtan, reprint-2005, Gandushadividhi Adhyaya Page No.553, Shlok No. 10.
 29. Dr. Bhrumhanand Tripathi- Astang Hrudayam (Sutrasthana), Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishtan, edition reprint 2017. Page No.249. Nasyavidhi Adhyaya 20/31.
 30. Kaviraja Dr. Ambikadutta Shastri - Sushruta Samhita, Chikitsasthana, Part-1, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint-2017, Dhumnasyakavalgruhachikitsa Adhyaya Page No.229, Shlok No. 63.
 31. Prof.K.R. Srikantha Murthy- Sarngadhara- Samhita, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Reprint edition- 2017, Gandushakavalapratيسانavidhi adhyaya Page No. 233, Shlok No.6,7.
 32. Kaviraja Dr. Ambikadutta Shastri - Sushruta Samhita, Chikitsasthana, Part-1, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, reprint-2017, Dhumnasyakavalgruhachikitsa

Adhyaya Page No.229, Shlok No.65.

33. Prof.K.R. Srikantha Murthy- Sarngadhara- Samhita, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Reprint edition- 2017, Gandushakavalapratissaranvidhi adhyaya Page No. 233, Shlok No.10.
34. Madhushree Das et al. Epidemiology Of Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis: A Review. International Journal Of Oral Health And Medical Research |ISSN 2395-7387| MARCH - APRIL 2017| VOL-3|ISSUE 6